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Research Article

Method Development and Validation for Estimation of Dapagliflozin and Linagliptin in Combined Dosage form by UV Spectrophotometry

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the present study was to develop, validate and statistically compare two new simple, rapid and reliable UV methods for simultaneous determination of dapagliflozin and linagliptin in combined dosage form. The methods selected for the present study were simultaneous equation and area under curve methods. Both the methods satisfied the Beer-Lambert's law in the range of 5-30 µg/mL with a low correlation coefficient. Percent relative standard deviation for inter- and intra-day variations as well as for repeatability was found to be less than 2% which suggests that the methods are precise. The limit of detection and limit of quantitation amounts measured by both the methods were observed to be very small indicating that the methods are highly sensitive. The proposed methods were applied for the estimation of the drugs in marketed tablet formulation and the percentage content of both the drugs measured by the proposed methods were found to be between 97 and 103%. The outcomes of one-way ANOVA demonstrated that the developed methods differ little from each other. Hence, both the proposed methods are found to be simple, economical, sensitive, accurate and precise and can be applied for the simultaneous estimation of dapagliflozin and linagliptin pharmaceutical formulation.

INTRODUCTION

The most widespread form of diabetes is type 2 diabetes mellitus that is affecting millions of people across the globe.^[1] Metformin is conventionally the initial oral antidiabetic agent of choice in the management of Type 2 diabetes

mellitus (T2DM) based on its many years proven track record of effectiveness, cost, neutrality with respect to weight gain and other positive safety profile.^[2,3] However, as the condition advances, metformin monotherapy is no longer effective enough. Metformin is normally used together with other medications to treat this condition and to

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improve blood sugar levels.^[4-6] In this aspect, a fixed-dose combination of two categories of anti-diabetic agents with complementary mechanisms of action lowers the dose and the chances of dose-related adverse effects. It is also possible that this strategy will enable the use of individual antidiabetic agents and thereby minimize the number of pills, improve adherence, and attain target HbA1c sooner compared with monotherapy.^[7-9]

Dipeptidyl peptidase 4 (DPP-4) and sodium-glucose cotransporter-2 (SGLT2) inhibitors used as a combination therapy may represent an effective approach to patients who do not attain sufficient control with metformin or to patients intolerant to metformin.^[10] As an inhibitor of SGLT2, dapagliflozin (DGF) in the joint protocol has the potential not only to reduce the level of blood sugar by inhibiting renal glucose reabsorption but also to cause a decrease in the number of hypoglycemic episodes since it does not rely on insulin secretion. Meanwhile, DGF possesses the benefit of both weight reduction and the decreased risk of endpoint events, which have been popular in the overweight T2DM population.^[11] Linagliptin, as a DPP-4 inhibitor, has not only the effect of enhancing insulin levels secretion but also the effect of controlling blood sugar level through inhibition of glucagon levels secretion. Linagliptin, in comparison to other DPP-4 inhibitors, is primarily excreted via nonrenal routes. Therefore, patients with impaired renal functions do not require dosage modifications.^[12,13] The synergistic mechanism of action and the good tolerance profiles of the two drug classes make them appropriate choice of treatment when used in combination therapy with any of the already existing glucose-lowering agents including insulin.^[9]

Although the efficacy of LGP and DGF is proved, a large analytical method gap exists to quantify these drugs simultaneously in combination therapy. A substantial literature search was conducted which indicated the existence of numerous ways of the estimation of DGF separately with the help of analysis methods like UV Spectroscopy, RP-HPLC method^[14,15] or in combination with other drugs like metformin or saxagliptin or others with the help of analysis methods like HPLC, RP-HPLC, HPLC-PDA, RP-UPLC, HPTLC, etc.^[16-23] Equally, the estimation of LGP alone is also described in many ways such as HPTLC, UV Spectroscopy^[24-26] or combined with other drugs like metformin or empagliflozin or other drugs using analytical techniques such as HPLC-UV, HPTLC, RP-HPLC.^[19,27-33] Out of the literature review it was observed that methods such as HPLC, HPLC-PDA, RP-HPLC, HPTLC are only a few methods to estimate DGF and LGP in combined dosage form.^[34-37] There is only a single UV spectrophotometric procedure that is available but it is not applicable to the combined dosage form, it is only applicable to the API.^[38] Thus, the objective of the current work was to establish and to validate two easy, fast and robust UV methods to determine DGF and LGP simultaneously in combined dosage form.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The reference samples of DGF and LGP were procured as gift sample from Morepen Labs Ltd., Parwanoo, Himachal Pradesh, India. The commercial formulation, DAPAVEL-L, marketed by Intas Pharmaceuticals Ltd., India (tablets containing 10 mg of DGF and 5 mg of LGP) was purchased from the local market. Throughout the experiment, analytical-grade materials and fresh purified distilled water was used.

Preparation of Standard Stock Solution

Accurately weighed quantity of 100 mg of DGF and 100 mg of LGP were transferred into 100 mL volumetric flasks individually containing 20 mL of methanol and the volume was made up to the mark with distilled water. These were stock solutions of strength of $1000 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of both DGF and LGP.

Preparation of Working Standard Solution

From standard stock solutions of DGF and LGP, 10 mL solution was transferred in to 100 mL volumetric flasks and diluted up to mark with distilled water individually. These were stock solution of strength of $100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of both DGF and LGP. Aliquots from these secondary stock solutions were appropriately diluted with distilled

water to obtain working standard solutions of concentration $10 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of both the drugs.

Selection of Wavelength

Simultaneous Equation Method (Method I)

The scanning of working standard solutions of DGF and LGP were carried out using Shimadzu UV1800 Double Beam UV-Visible Spectrophotometer in the range of 200–400 nm against distilled water as a blank. The maximum absorbance (λ_{max}) of DGF and LGP was detected at 222.5 nm (λ_1) and 227.5 nm (λ_2), respectively (Figure 1 and 2).

Figure 1. UV spectrum of dapagliflozin

Figure 2. UV spectrum of linagliptin

AUC Method (Method II)

The area under the curve (AUC) technique is a spectrophotometric technique that is utilized in the

simultaneous analysis of mixtures of components especially where the mixtures have broad spectra or no sharp peaks. The AUC approach is based on the principle that the area of a part of the spectrum of a mixture is proportional to the concentration of a given component in that area.

In this method, wavelength range 212.5 nm (λ_3) to 232.5 nm (λ_4) was selected for estimation of DGF and 217.5 nm (λ_5) to 237.5 nm (λ_6) was selected for estimation of LGP.

Preparation of Calibration Curve

Method I

From the secondary standard solutions of DGF ($100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) and LGP ($100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$), aliquots of 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 mL were transferred into series of 100 mL volumetric flask and diluted up to mark with distilled water. These were solutions of 5-30 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of both the drugs. The corresponding absorbance were measured at 222.5 nm (λ_1) and 227.5 nm (λ_2). Calibration curves were plotted by taking concentration on x-axis and absorbance on y-axis which showed straight lines. Absorptivity (a) for both the drugs were calculated by the formula:

$$a = A/C$$

Where, A= absorbance, C= concentration of analyte in $\text{g}100 \text{ mL}^{-1}$

Method II

From working standard solution of DGF ($100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) and LGP ($100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$), aliquots of 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 mL were transferred separately into series of 100 mL volumetric flasks and diluted up to mark with distilled water. This yielded solutions of 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of both the drugs. The corresponding AUC of all the solutions of DGF were calculated in the range

212.5 nm (λ_3) to 232.5 nm (λ_4) and AUC of all the solutions of LGP were calculated in the range 217.5 nm (λ_5) to 237.5 nm (λ_6). Calibration curves were plotted by taking concentration on x-axis and AUC on y-axis which showed a straight line.

Preparation of Test Solution for Assay Determination

Dapagliflozin/Linagliptin is used in the ratio of 10/5 mg for treatment of diabetes. Ten tablets of Dapavel-L 10/5 tablets were weighed and powdered in a mortar pestle and powder equivalent to 50 mg of DGF was taken into a 50 mL volumetric flask containing 10 mL methanol. The contents of the flask were sonicated for 15 min. to completely dissolve the active ingredients. The volume was made up to mark with distilled water and the solution filtered using Whatman filter paper no. 41 in order to obtain test stock solution that correspond to $1000 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of DGF and $500 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of LGP. An aliquot of this solution (2 mL) was pipetted into a 100 mL volumetric flask and the volume was brought up to the mark with distilled water. This test solution containing working concentrations of $20 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ DGF and $10 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ LGP was analyzed for assay determination.

Analysis of Marketed Formulation

Method I

When two absorbing drugs are present in a sample and each absorbs at λ_{max} of the other, it could be possible to determine both drugs using simultaneous equation technique. Two wavelengths selected for the development of the simultaneous equation were 222.5 nm and 227.5 nm. The absorptivity values determined for DGF were 449.78 (a_{x1}), 424.86 (a_{x2}) and for LGP were 445.14 (a_{y1}) and 497.42 (a_{y2}), respectively at 222.5 nm and 227.5 nm. These values were the

means of six estimations. The absorptivity data are shown in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1. Absorptivity data for dapagliflozin

Sr. No.	Conc. (g/100 mL)	Abs. at 222.5 nm	ax ₁ at 222.5 nm	Abs. at 227.5 nm	ax ₂ at 227.5 nm
1.	0.0005	0.251	430.00	0.206	411.90
2.	0.0010	0.443	443.00	0.425	425.10
3.	0.0015	0.732	488.00	0.663	441.99
4.	0.0020	0.912	456.00	0.861	430.50
5.	0.0025	1.105	442.00	1.055	422.00
6.	0.0030	1.319	439.67	1.253	417.67
Average			449.78		424.86

Table 2. Absorptivity data for linagliptin

Sr. No.	Conc. (µg/mL)	Abs. at 222.5 nm (n = 6)	ay ₁ at 222.5 nm	Abs. at 227.5 nm (n = 6)	ay ₂ at 227.5 nm
1.	0.0005	0.235	470.00	0.253	506.00
2.	0.0010	0.483	483.00	0.494	494.00
3.	0.0015	0.662	441.33	0.771	514.00
4.	0.0020	0.868	434.00	1.009	504.50
5.	0.0025	1.063	425.20	1.220	488.00
6.	0.0030	1.252	417.33	1.434	478.00
Average			445.14		497.42

The concentration of two drugs of mixture at these wavelengths can be calculated using following equation (1) and (2):

$$C_x = \frac{A_1 * ay_2 - A_2 * ay_1}{ax_1 * ay_2 - ax_2 * ay_1} \quad (1)$$

$$C_y = \frac{A_2 * ax_1 - A_1 * ax_2}{ax_1 * ay_2 - ax_2 * ay_1} \quad (2)$$

Where, A₁ and A₂ are absorbance of mixture at 222.5 nm and 227.5 nm;

C_x and C_y are the unknown concentration of DGF and LGP, respectively in sample solution;

- ax₁ = Absorptivity of DGF at λ₁
- ay₁ = Absorptivity of LGP at λ₁
- ax₂ = Absorptivity of DGF at λ₂
- ay₂ = Absorptivity of LGP at λ₂

Method II

The area and absorptivity values were calculated at each wavelength range and the concentration of both the drugs was calculated from the equations:

$$A_1 = ax_1 C(x) + ay_1 C(y) \quad (\lambda_3 - \lambda_4) \text{ nm} \quad (3)$$

$$A_2 = ax_2 C(x) + ay_2 C(y) \quad (\lambda_5 - \lambda_6) \text{ nm} \quad (4)$$

$$C_{(x)} = [A_1 \times ay_2 - A_2 \times ay_1] / [ax_1 \times ay_2 - ax_2 \times ay_1] \quad (5)$$

$$C_{(y)} = [A_2 \times ax_1 - A_1 \times ax_2] / [ax_1 \times ay_2 - ax_2 \times ay_1] \quad (6)$$

where,

- ax₁ and ax₂ are absorptivities of DGF at (λ₃-λ₄) and (λ₅-λ₆) respectively.
- ay₁ and ay₂ are absorptivities of LGP at (λ₃-λ₄) and (λ₅-λ₆) respectively.

- A_1 and A_2 are AUC of the formulation at (λ_3 - λ_4) and (λ_5 - λ_6) respectively.
- $C_{(x)}$ and $C_{(y)}$ are the concentration of DGF (x) and LGP (y), respectively.

Method Validation

Linearity and Range

Linearity was studied by preparing standard solutions of DGF and LGP at six different concentrations i.e. 5-30 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$.

Method I: For each solution, the absorbance of both the drugs was measured at both the wavelengths 222.5 (i.e. λ_{max} of DGF) and 227.5 nm (i.e. λ_{max} of LGP). The absorbance versus concentration calibration curves were plotted. Linear regression analysis showed the linearity of the absorbance responses versus concentrations.

Method II: For each solution of DGF, the AUC was calculated in the range 212.5 nm to 232.5 nm and for LGP, AUC was measured in the range 217.5 to 237.5 nm. The calibration curves of AUC versus concentration were plotted.

Precision

The precision of the proposed method was assessed as repeatability, intra-day precision and inter-day precision.

Repeatability was performed by applying six replicates of sample analysis. 5 mL of secondary stock solution ($100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) of LGP standard was transferred to a 100 mL volumetric flask. 10 mL of secondary stock solution of DGF standard ($100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) was transferred to the above 100 mL volumetric flask. The volume was adjusted up to mark with distilled water to get $10 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ solution of DGF and $5 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ solution of LGP.

For intermediate precision, aliquots of 5, 10 and 15 mL of secondary stock solutions ($100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) of LGP were transferred to a series of 100 mL volumetric flask. Aliquots of 10, 20 and 30 mL of secondary stock solution of DGF ($100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) were respectively transferred to the same series of 100 mL volumetric flask. The volume was adjusted up to mark with distilled water to get 10, 20, and $30 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ solutions of DGF and 5, 10 and $15 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ solutions of LGP. Intra- day and inter-day precision of the proposed method was conducted by analyzing the corresponding responses triplicate on the same day and on three different days, respectively to the above solutions and the results are expressed in relative standard deviation (RSD).

Accuracy

Recovery studies were carried out by standard addition method. The standard addition method was performed at three concentration levels in triplicate at 50%, 100% and 150%. All the dilutions were prepared from $100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of standard and sample stock solutions. A known amount of standard DGF (5, 10 and $15 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) and LGP (2.5, 5 and $7.5 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) similar to 50%, 100% and 150% of the label claim were added to test solution of DGF ($10 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) and LGP ($5 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$), respectively. The solutions were analyzed in triplicate at each level as per the proposed method. Each recovery was made three times and average value was considered. The percent recovery at each level was calculated.

LOD and LOQ

The LOD and LOQ were estimated from the set of six calibration curves used to determine method linearity by using the following equations:

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 * \sigma/S \text{ and}$$

$$LOQ = 10 \cdot \sigma / S$$

Where,

σ = the standard deviation of y- intercepts of regression lines of six calibration curves,

S = the average of the slopes of six calibration curves.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Method Validation

Linearity

The response for the both the drugs was found to be linear in the concentration range of 5-30 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for both the methods with good linearity (correlation coefficient, r^2 more than 0.99) (Figure 3,4 and5).

The linearity results are given in Tables 3 to 6. Correlation coefficients for both the drugs at all the wavelengths studied were found to close to 1 which proved the good linearity.

Table 3. Linearity data of linagliptin and dapagliflozin at λ_1

Sr. No.	Dapagliflozin at λ_1			Linagliptin at λ_1		
	Conc. (g 100 mL ⁻¹)	Abs.* \pm SD	% RSD	Conc. (g 100 mL ⁻¹)	Abs.* \pm SD	% RSD
1.	0.0005	0.215 \pm 0.0023	1.07	0.0005	0.235 \pm 0.0034	1.447
2.	0.0010	0.443 \pm 0.0035	0.790	0.0010	0.483 \pm 0.0030	0.621
3.	0.0015	0.732 \pm 0.0131	1.790	0.0015	0.662 \pm 0.0051	0.770
4.	0.0020	0.912 \pm 0.0106	1.162	0.0020	0.868 \pm 0.0122	1.406
5.	0.0025	1.105 \pm 0.0111	1.005	0.0025	1.063 \pm 0.0092	0.865
6.	0.0030	1.319 \pm 0.0101	0.766	0.0030	1.252 \pm 0.0112	0.895

*Average of six determinations

Figure 3. Standard plots of linagliptin for method I

Table 4. Linearity data of linagliptin and dapagliflozin at λ_2

Sr. No.	Dapagliflozin at λ_2			Linagliptin at λ_2		
	Conc. (g/100 mL)	Abs.* \pm SD	% RSD	Conc. (g/100 mL)	Abs.* \pm SD	% RSD
1.	0.0005	0.201 \pm 0.0021	1.045	0.0005	0.253 \pm 0.0025	0.988
2.	0.0010	0.425 \pm 0.0052	1.224	0.0010	0.494 \pm 0.0083	1.680
3.	0.0015	0.663 \pm 0.0079	1.191	0.0015	0.771 \pm 0.0104	1.349

4.	0.0020	0.861±0.0063	0.732	0.0020	1.009±0.0151	1.497
5.	0.0025	1.035±0.0093	0.899	0.0025	1.220±0.0098	0.803
6.	0.0030	1.223±0.0109	0.891	0.0030	1.434±0.0127	0.886

*Average of six determinations

Figure 4. Standard plots of dapagliflozin for method I

Table 5. Linearity data of dapagliflozin and linagliptin for Method II

Dapagliflozin at λ_1 and λ_2		Linagliptin between λ_3 and λ_4	
Conc. (g/100 mL)	AUC*	Conc. (g/100 mL)	AUC*
0.0005	3.756154	0.0005	3.730479
0.0010	8.94204	0.0010	7.79154
0.0015	13.68856	0.0015	12.46566
0.0020	17.26324	0.0020	16.37335
0.0025	20.5264	0.0025	19.73071
0.0030	25.72331	0.0030	23.96976

*Average of six determinations

Figure 5. Standard plots of dapagliflozin and linagliptin for method II

Table 6. Linearity results of dapagliflozin and linagliptin for method II

Parameter	Dapagliflozin	Linagliptin
Range (µg/mL)	5-30	5-30
Correlation coefficient	0.9967	0.9985
Slope	8484.8	7955.2
Intercept	0.0185	0.0227

Precision

The %RSD of repeatability was found to be less than 2% for both the developed methods (Table 7). The %RSD of intraday and interday precision was also found to be less than 2% for both the methods, thus, confirming precision of the developed methods (Tables 8 and 9).

Table 7. Repeatability test of dapagliflozin and linagliptin

Sr. No.	Method I				Method II			
	Absorbance		Concentration (µg mL ⁻¹)		AUC		Concentration (µg mL ⁻¹)	
	222.5 nm	227.5 nm	DGF	LGP	212.5 nm to 232.5 nm	217.5 nm to 237.5 nm	DGF	LGP
1.	0.728	0.674	9.9414	5.0587	0.529530	0.427590	9.8199	5.0901
2.	0.733	0.494	10.1258	4.9615	0.528057	0.426326	9.7600	5.1100
3.	0.727	0.673	9.9331	5.0457	0.532995	0.430768	10.0499	4.9501
4.	0.727	0.671	10.0756	4.8838	0.536576	0.433450	10.0249	5.0801
5.	0.730	0.675	10.0295	5.0036	0.539656	0.436024	10.1199	5.0701
6.	0.732	0.676	10.1175	4.9485	0.523716	0.423212	9.8502	4.8898
	S.D.		0.0847	0.0657			0.1459	0.0896
	%RSD		0.844	1.318			1.469	1.781

Table 8. Intraday precision test of dapagliflozin and linagliptin

Sr. No.	Method I				Method II			
	Absorbance		Concentration (µg mL ⁻¹)		AUC		Concentration (µg mL ⁻¹)	
	222.5 nm	227.5 nm	DGF	LGP	212.5 nm to 232.5 nm	217.5 nm to 237.5 nm	DGF	LGP
1.	0.731	0.674	10.1804	4.8546	0.526327	0.425270	9.8767	4.9378
2.	0.725	0.670	9.9876	4.9388	0.544147	0.439633	10.1956	5.1212
3.	0.726	0.672	9.9247	5.0328	0.536486	0.433582	10.1125	4.9859
	S.D.		0.1332	0.0891			0.1654	0.0951
	%RSD		1.328	1.804			1.644	1.896
4.	1.472	1.361	20.2306	10.0817	1.069150	0.864207	20.2105	9.8761
5.	1.495	1.381	20.6369	10.1367	1.063158	0.858710	19.8121	10.1189
6.	1.501	1.385	20.8297	10.0525	1.080759	0.873102	20.2168	10.2062
	S.D.		0.3058	0.0428			0.2319	0.1710
	%RSD		1.487	0.424			1.155	1.699
7.	2.191	2.025	30.168	14.9428	1.607873	1.299945	30.5171	14.7240
8.	2.172	2.008	29.8664	14.8586	1.610328	1.300911	30.1192	15.2112
9.	2.159	1.996	29.6864	14.7712	1.5781370	1.274997	29.5571	14.8653
	S.D.		0.2433	0.0858			0.4823	0.2507
	%RSD		0.814	0.578			1.604	1.679

Table 9. Interday precision test of dapagliflozin and linagliptin

Sr. No.	Method I		Method II	
	Absorbance	Concentration (µg mL ⁻¹)	AUC	Concentration (µg/mL)

	222.5 nm	227.5 nm	DGF	LGP	212.5 nm to 232.5 nm	217.5 nm to 237.5 nm	DGF	LGP
1.	0.733	0.677	10.1258	4.9615	0.526422	0.425319	9.8664	4.9514
2.	0.740	0.684	10.1844	5.0522	0.534242	0.431867	10.1132	4.9201
3.	0.717	0.663	9.8494	4.9162	0.544775	0.440205	10.2356	5.0976
	S.D.		0.1789	0.0693			0.1881	0.0947
	%RSD		1.780	1.392			1.867	1.899
4.	1.455	1.347	19.8745	10.1044	1.026071	0.829065	19.2563	9.6244
5.	1.438	1.329	19.8035	9.8032	1.038116	0.839247	19.6785	9.5323
6.	1.457	1.345	20.1763	9.8064	1.016879	0.822185	19.3225	9.2886
	S.D.		0.1980	0.1730			0.2271	0.1735
	%RSD		0.992	1.747			1.169	1.830
7.	2.188	2.025	29.9291	15.1469	1.632752	1.319569	30.7753	15.1755
8.	2.167	2.004	29.7533	14.8748	1.605823	1.298149	30.4177	14.7684
9.	2.227	2.059	30.6118	15.2472	1.579560	1.276640	29.7989	14.6537
	S.D.		0.4535	0.1927			0.4940	0.2742
	%RSD		1.507	1.277			1.629	1.845

Accuracy

Accuracy of the method was confirmed by recovery study from marketed formulation at three level of standard addition. Percentage recovery for DGF was in range of 97.03 – 102.22 %, while for

LGP, it was found to be in range of 96.88 – 102.02 % (Tables 10 to 13) which showed that the developed methods were accurate. The %RSD was also found to be less than 2% in both the methods and thus, confirming the accuracy of result.

Table 10. Accuracy data of dapagliflozin for method I

Conc. of Test sol. (µg/mL)	Standard added (µg/mL)	Abs. (n = 3) (at 222.5)	Abs. (n = 3) (at 227.5)	Total Amount Found (µg/mL)	Recovered amount (µg/mL)	% Recovery
10	0	0.448	0.424	9.8549	-	98.55
		0.460	0.435	10.1648		101.65
		0.457	0.432	10.2632		101.20
Average						100.47
S.D.						1.6751
%RSD						1.667
10	5	0.672	0.635	14.911	4.911	98.22
		0.680	0.643	15.0318	5.0318	100.63
		0.678	0.641	15.0016	5.0016	100.03
Average						99.63
S.D.						1.2546
%RSD						1.259
10	10	0.902	0.852	20.0577	10.0577	100.58
		0.894	0.845	19.8082	9.8082	98.08
		0.886	0.837	19.6874	9.6874	97.03
Average						98.56
S.D.						1.8237
%RSD						1.850
10	15	1.113	1.051	24.7888	14.788	98.59
		1.134	1.071	25.2347	15.2347	101.56
		1.149	1.087	25.3326	15.3326	102.22

Average	100.79
S.D.	1.9336
%RSD	1.919

Table 11. Accuracy data of linagliptin for method I

Conc. of Test sol. (µg/mL)	Standard added (µg/mL)	Abs. (n = 3) (at 222.5)	Abs. (n = 3) (at 227.5)	Total Amount Found (µg/mL)	Recovered amount (µg/mL)	% Recovery
5	0	0.224	0.250	5.0075	-	100.15
		0.226	0.252	5.0334	-	100.67
		0.218	0.244	4.9297	-	98.59
Average						99.80
S.D.						1.0825
%RSD						1.085
5	2.5	0.333	0.372	7.4723	2.4723	98.89
		0.336	0.375	7.5112	2.5112	100.45
		0.331	0.370	7.4464	2.4464	97.86
Average						99.07
S.D.						1.3040
%RSD						1.316
5	5	0.448	0.500	10.0642	5.0642	101.28
		0.441	0.493	9.9243	4.9243	98.49
		0.440	0.492	9.8844	4.8844	97.69
Average						99.15
S.D.						1.8847
%RSD						1.901
5	7.5	0.557	0.622	12.4798	7.4798	99.73
		0.546	0.610	12.2657	7.2657	96.88
		0.558	0.623	12.5353	7.5353	100.47
Average						99.03
S.D.						1.8955
%RSD						1.914

Table 12. Accuracy data of dapagliflozin for method II

Conc. of Test sol. (µg/mL)	Standard added (µg/mL)	AUC (212.5 nm to 232.5 nm)	AUC (217.5 nm to 237.5 nm)	Total Amount Found (µg/mL)	Recovered amount (µg/mL)	% Recovery
10	0	0.354937	0.294087	9.8450	-	98.45
		0.362543	0.300390	10.056		100.56
		0.365753	0.303048	10.1450		101.45
Average						100.15
SD						1.540790
%RSD						1.5384
10	5	0.543203	0.450077	15.0670	5.0670	101.34
		0.541599	0.448748	15.0225	5.0225	100.45
		0.536948	0.444894	14.8935	4.8935	97.87
Average						99.89
SD						1.802286
%RSD						1.8043
10	10	0.728693	0.603767	20.2120	10.2120	102.12
		0.725484	0.601108	20.1230	10.1230	101.23

		0.716652	0.593790	19.8780	9.8780	98.78
Average						100.71
SD						1.729653
%RSD						1.7176
10	15	0.907477	0.751901	25.1710	15.1710	101.14
		0.887522	0.735367	24.6175	14.6175	97.45
		0.894931	0.741505	24.8230	14.8230	98.82
Average						99.14
SD						1.865270
%RSD						1.8815

Table 13. Accuracy data of linagliptin for method II

Conc. of Test sol. (µg/mL)	Standard added (µg/mL)	AUC (212.5 nm to 232.5 nm)	AUC (217.5 nm to 237.5 nm)	Total Amount Found (µg/mL)	Recovered amount (µg/mL)	% Recovery
5	0	0.170053	0.130088	4.9320	-	98.64
		0.175881	0.134546	5.1012	-	102.02
		0.171650	0.131309	4.9786	-	99.57
Average						100.08
S.D.						1.7460
%RSD						1.745
5	2.5	0.256436	0.196169	7.4376	2.4376	97.50
		0.259570	0.198566	7.5285	2.5285	101.14
		0.258160	0.197488	7.4876	2.4876	99.50
Average						99.38
S.D.						1.8230
%RSD						1.834
5	5	0.342455	0.261973	9.9325	4.9325	98.65
		0.347852	0.266100	10.089	5.0890	101.78
		0.347093	0.265520	10.067	5.0670	101.34
Average						100.59
S.D.						1.6944
%RSD						1.685
5	7.5	0.425238	0.325300	12.3335	7.3335	97.78
		0.427255	0.326843	12.3920	7.3920	98.56
		0.434158	0.332123	12.5922	7.5922	101.23
Average						99.19
S.D.						1.8092
%RSD						1.824

LOD and LOQ

Table 14 demonstrates the LOD and LOQ values calculated by standard formula provided in ICH

guidelines. The low values of LOD and LOQ in both the methods indicated that predicted methods are very sensitive.

Table 14. LOD and LOQ data

Drug	Method I				Method II	
	At 222.5 nm		At 227.5 nm		LOD (µg/mL)	LOQ (µg/mL)
	LOD (µg/mL)	LOQ (µg/mL)	LOD (µg/mL)	LOQ (µg/mL)		
DGF	2.3	6.96	1.89	5.74	2.19	7.12

LGP	1.33	4.02	1.56	4.73	1.89	6.14
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Assay of Linagliptin and Dapagliflozin in the Marketed Formulation

The developed methods were applied to test sample solution preparation. The % assay of DGF and LGP was $100.843 \pm 1.869\%$ and $100.277 \pm 1.913\%$, respectively of the labelled amount by

method I (Table 15). Whereas, the % assay of DGF and LGP was found to be $99.73 \pm 1.611\%$ and $100.42 \pm 1.645\%$, respectively of the labelled amount by method II (Table 16). These methods were successfully used by several researchers for simultaneous estimation of various drugs.^[39-45]

Table 15. Analysis of test solution by method I

Sr. No.	Absorbance at 222.5 nm	Absorbance at 227.5 nm	Amount of DGF in the sample (mg)	Amount of LGP in the sample (mg)	% of DGF in Label claimed	% of LGP in Label claimed
1.	1.466	1.356	50.2728	25.2124	100.50	100.80
2.	1.482	1.366	51.6766	24.5159	103.303	98.016
3.	1.455	1.346	49.8645	25.0585	99.681	100.186
4.	1.447	1.341	49.1625	25.4068	98.278	101.578
5.	1.476	1.367	50.3038	25.7387	100.559	102.905
6.	1.477	1.362	51.3938	24.5564	102.738	98.178
Average					100.843	100.277
S.D.					1.8852	1.9183
%RSD					1.869	1.913

Table 16. Analysis of test solution by method II

Sr. No.	AUC (212.5 nm to 232.5 nm)	AUC (217.5 nm to 237.5 nm)	Amount of DGF in the sample (mg)	Amount of LGP in the sample (mg)	% of DGF in Label claimed	% of LGP in Label claimed
1.	1.057428	0.854148	49.3354	25.0855	98.62	100.29
2.	1.077630	0.870571	50.3921	25.4454	100.74	101.73
3.	1.085593	0.877021	50.7830	25.6140	101.52	102.41
4.	1.041437	0.841305	48.6699	24.6218	97.29	98.44
5.	1.065266	0.860465	49.6856	25.2876	99.32	101.10
6.	1.067653	0.863006	50.4654	24.6453	100.88	98.53
Average					99.73	100.42
S.D.					1.6063	1.6521
%RSD					1.611	1.645

Statistical Comparison of Simultaneous Equation and AUC Methods by One Way ANOVA

The statistical methods were used to analyze the data of the assays to identify the effect of the two projected approaches. The statistical significance

of the differences between the two different approaches was compared using one-way ANOVA. The two tests were established at $p < 0.05$. Table 17 illustrates the results of one-way ANOVA and it was observed that the developed procedures were not substantially different between one another.^[46]

Table 17. Statistical comparison of assay results utilizing one way ANOVA

Drug	Method	Mean	Variance	F	F crit	p-value
Dapagliflozin	Simultaneous Equation	100.8432	3.5541	1.2157	4.9646	0.2960
	AUC	99.7283	2.5801			
Linagliptin	Simultaneous Equation	100.2772	3.6797	0.0182	4.9646	0.8953
	AUC	100.4167	2.7296			

The calculated F-statistic is lesser than the F-critical value and p-value is more than 0.05 which suggests that the variance between groups is not significant.

CONCLUSION

Two different UV spectrophotometric methods i.e. simultaneous estimation equation method and area under curve method have been proposed for simultaneous estimation of dapagliflozin and linagliptin in pure and tablet dosage form using mixture of water and methanol as solvent. Both the methods fulfilled the Beer-Lambert law within 5-30 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ with low correlation coefficient. Recovery studies were conducted by adding known quantity of standard drug to pre analyzed sample and it was found that the percentage recovery was within the limits. The reproducibility of the methods was revealed by % RSD for inter and intra-day variations which was found to be less than 2. The repeatability test also showed that RSD for the two methods was less than 2 percent and this further indicated that the two methods are precise. The amounts of LOD and LOQ calculated by the two methods were found to be very small hence the predicted methods are very sensitive. The techniques proposed were used to estimate the drugs in marketed tablet dosage form and very encouraging results were obtained. The percentage content of both the drugs determined by the proposed methods were found within the range of 97-103%. The statistical significance of these two different methods was compared using One-way ANOVA. The results of one-way ANOVA indicate that the devised methods are not very

different. Therefore, it can be concluded that both the proposed techniques are simple, economical, precise, accurate and sensitive and may be applied in the simultaneous estimation of dapagliflozin and linagliptin pharmaceutical dosage form.

Statements and Declarations

The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.

REFERENCES

1. Sun, H.; Saeedi, P.; Karuranga, S.; Pinkepank, M.; Ogurtsova, K.; Duncan, B.B.; Stein, C.; Basit, A.; Chan, J.C.N.; Mbanya, J.C.; et al. IDF diabetes Atlas: global, regional and country-level diabetes prevalence estimates for 2021 and projections for 2045. *Diabetes Res. Clin. Pract.* 2022, 183, 109119. DOI: 10.1016/j.diabres.2021.109119.
2. Inzucchi, S.E.; Bergenstal, R.M.; Buse, J.B.; Diamant, M.; Ferrannini, E.; Nauck, M.; Peters, A.L.; Tsapas, A.; Wender, R.; Matthews, D.R. Management of hyperglycemia in type 2 diabetes, 2015: a patient-centered approach: update to a position statement of the American Diabetes Association and the European Association for the Study of diabetes. *Diabetes Care*. 2015, 38, 140-149. DOI: 10.2337/dc14-2441.
3. Bae, J.H.; Han, K.D.; Ko, S.H.; Yang, Y.S.; Choi, J.H.; Choi, K.M.; Kwon, H.-S.; Won, K.C. Diabetes fact sheet in Korea 2021. *Diabetes Metab. J.* 2022, 46, 417-426. DOI: 10.4093/dmj.2022.0106.

4. Yan, Y.;Xuefeng, Y. See the role of metformin in the drug treatment of type 2 diabetes from the guide update. *Chin. J. Pract. Intern. Med.*2022,42(11),884–888. DOI: 10.20452/pamw.16511.
5. Fonseca, V.A. Defining and characterizing the progression of type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes Care.*2009,32(Suppl 2),S151-S156. DOI: 10.2337/dc09-S301.
6. Hong, J.H.; Kim, M.J.; Min, K.W.; Won, J.C.; Kim, T.N.; Lee, B.-W.; Kang, J.G.; Kim, J.H.; Park, J.H.; Ku, B.J.; et al. Efficacy and safety of a fixed-dose combination of dapagliflozin and linagliptin (AJU-A51) in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus: A multicentre, randomized, double-blind, parallel-group, placebo-controlled phase III study. *Diabetes Obes. Metab.*2025,27,81–91. DOI:10.1111/dom.15985.
7. Chadha, M.; Das, A.K.; Deb, P.; Gangopadhyay, K.K.; Joshi, S.; Kesavadev, J.; Kovil, R.; Kumar, S.; Misra, A.; Mohan, V. Expert opinion: Optimum clinical approach to combination-use of SGLT2i + DPP4i in the Indian diabetes setting. *Diabetes Ther.*2022,13,1097–1114. DOI: 10.1007/s13300-022-01219-x.
8. Kim, S.W.; Baik, S.H.; Yoon, K.H.; Lee, H.W.; Filozof, C. Efficacy and safety of vildagliptin/pioglitazone combination therapy in Korean patients with diabetes. *World J. Diabetes.*2010,1,153–160. DOI: 10.4239/wjd.v1.i5.153.
9. Kumthekar, P.; Upadhyay, M.R.; Tamma, R.R.; Kranti, V.; Bhattacharya, R.; Sharma, P.K.; Barge, V.K.B.; Revankar, S.; Ghatge, S. Fixed-dose Combination of Dapagliflozin and Linagliptin in Individuals with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Inadequately Controlled on Metformin: A Randomized Double-blind Multicenter Trial. *Journal of Diabetology.* 2025,16(1),50-56. DOI: 10.4103/jod.jod_169_24.
10. Sharma, M.D. Potential for combination of dipeptidyl peptidase-4 inhibitors and sodium-glucose co-transporter-2 inhibitors for the treatment of type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes Obes. Metab.*2015,17,616–621. DOI: 10.1111/dom.12451.
11. Mingli, H.; Li, J.; Su, Z.; Xinrong, Y. Comparison of the efficacy of dapagliflozin and linagliptin in the treatment of type 2 diabetes patients with normal body mass index and poor metformin monotherapy. *Traditional Medicine and Modern Medicine.*2024,7, 85-91. DOI: 10.1142/S2575900024500058.
12. Blech, S.; Ludwig-Schwelling, E.; Gräfe-Mody, E.U.; Withopf, B.; Wagner, K. The metabolism and disposition of the oral dipeptidyl peptidase-4 inhibitor, linagliptin, in humans. *Drug Metab. Dispos.*2010,38,667-678. DOI: 10.1124/dmd.109.031476.
13. Friedrich, C.; Emser, A.; Woerle, H.J.; Graefe-Mody, U. Renal impairment has no clinically relevant effect on the long-term exposure of linagliptin in patients with type 2 diabetes. *Am. J. Ther.*2013,20,618-621. DOI: 10.1097/MJT.0b013e31826232dc.
14. Mante, G.V.; Gupta, K.R.; Trayambkarao, A. Estimation of dapagliflozin from its tablet formulation by UV-spectrometry. *Pharma. Methods.*2017,8(2),102-107. DOI: 10.5530/phm.2017.8.16.
15. Mante, G.V.; Hemke, A.T.; Umekar, M.J. RP-HPLC methods for estimation of Dapagliflozin from its Tablet. *Int. J. ChemTech Res.*2018,11(1),242-248.
16. Manoharan, G.; Ismaiel, A.M.; Ahmed, Z.M. Stability indicating RP-HPLC Method development for simultaneous determination of dapagliflozin in raw and tablet formulation. *Chem. Res. J.*2018,3(2),159-164.

17. Madhvi, S.;Rani, A.P. Development and Validation of a method for simultaneous determination of Dapagliflozin and Saxagliptin in a formulation by RP-UPLC. *World J. Pharm. Res.* 2017,6(12),904-916. DOI: 10.20959/wjpr201712-9703.
18. Urooj, A.;Sundar, P.S.;Vasanthi, R.; Raja, L.A.;Dutt, K.R.; Rao, K.N.V.;Hamana, H. Development and Validation of RP-HPLC Method for Simultaneous estimation of Dapagliflozin and Metformin in Bulk and in synthetic mixture. *World J. Pharmacy Pharm. Sci.* 2017,6(7),2139-2150. DOI: 10.20959/wjpps20177-9657.
19. Kant, R.;Babu, R.; Kapoor, G.;Bhutani, R. Optimization of a single HPLC-PDA method for quantifying metformin, gliclazide, pioglitazone, dapagliflozin, empagliflozin, saxagliptin, linagliptin and teneligliptin using central composite design. *Bioorg. Chem.* 2019,91,103111. DOI: 10.1016/j.bioorg.2019.103111.
20. Godge, R.K.;Shinde, G.S.; Joshi, S. Simultaneous estimation and validation of dapagliflozin and saxagliptin in bulk drug and dosage form by RP-HPLC. *Res. J. Sci. Tech.* 2019,11(1),59-63. DOI: 10.5958/2349-2988.2019.00008.1.
21. Nasser, S.;Salama, I.; Mustafa, S.M. Comparative HPLC and HPTLC study for simultaneous determination of dapagliflozin and metformin hydrochloride in bulk and pharmaceutical formulation. *J. Planar Chromatogr.* 2018,31,469-476. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1556/1006.2018.31.6.7>.
22. Abdelrahman, A.E.; Maher, H.M.;Alzoman, A.N. HPTLC method for determination of metformin hydrochloride, saxagliptin and dapagliflozin in pharmaceuticals. *Curr. Anal. Chem.* 2020,16(5),609619. DOI: 10.2174/1573407215666190131123029.
23. Padmaja, B.R.;Sivagami, B.;Chandrasekar, R.;Niranjan, M.A. highly validated RP_HPLC method development for simultaneous estimation of dapagliflozin and saxagliptin in tablet dosage form. *Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Drug Res.* 2018,10(5),372-378. DOI: 10.25004/IJPSTR.2018.100503.
24. Rao, K.V.; Gorla, R.;Sreenivasulu, B.;Sreenivas, N.; Kaleemullah, T.; Sharma, H.;Korupoulu, R.B. A Simple and sensitive stability-indicating HPTLC assay method for the determination of linagliptin. *Pharmacophore.* 2014,5(5),693-700.
25. Vijaya, S.K.;Anusha, A.;Sudhakar, M. UV-spectrometry method for estimation of linagliptin in bulk and pharmaceutical formulations. *Asian J. Res. Chem.* 2016,9(1),47-50. DOI: 10.5958/0974-4150.2016.00009.2.
26. Rajbanshi, J.C.;Alam, M.M.; Hossain, M.S.; Islam, M.S.;Rouf, A.S.S. Development and validation of a RP-HPLC method for quantitative analysis of linagliptin in bulk and dosage forms. *Dhaka Univer. J. Pharm. Sci.* 2018,17(2),175-182. DOI: 10.3329/dujps.v17i2.39173
27. Sivagami, B.;Purushotham, A.;Sikdar, P.; Chandrasekar, R.;Niranjan, M.A. validated method for the simultaneous estimation of linagliptin and metformin in tablet dosage forms by RP-HPLC. *Res. J. Pharm. Tech.* 2020,13(3),1266-1270. DOI: 10.5958/0974-360X.2020.00233.4.
28. Donepudi, S.;Achanta, S. Validated HPLC-UV method for simultaneous estimation of linagliptin and empagliflozin in human plasma. *Int. J. Appl. Pharmaceut.* 2018,10(3),56-61. DOI: 10.22159/ijap.2018v10i3.24662.
29. Varaprasad, C.; Md. Asif, Ramakrishna, K. RP-HPLC method for simultaneous

- estimation of metformin and linagliptin in tablet dosage form. *Rasayan J. Chem.* 2015, 8(4), 426-432.
30. Shirisha, S.; Haque, M.A.; Sireesha, D.; Bakshi, V.; Harshini, S. Development and validation of RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of metformin and linagliptin in combined pharmaceutical dosage form. *Int. J. Pharm Res. Health Sci.* 2014, 2(6), 491-495.
 31. Jillala, S.; Balekari, U.; Ciddi, V. Development and validation of stability indicating HPTLC method for simultaneous determination of linagliptin and metformin. *Int. J. Pharmacy Pharm. Sci.* 2016, 8(1), 112-115.
 32. Ravi, K.T.N.; Parvathi, P.; Suresh, J.N.K. Development and validation of RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous estimation of linagliptin, empagliflozin and metformin in solid dosage form. *Asian J. Pharm. Anal.* 2020, 10(3), 117-124.
 33. Bhole, R.P.; Wankhede, S.B.; Pandey, M. Stability indicating HPTLC method for simultaneous estimation of empagliflozin and linagliptin in pharmaceutical formulation. *Anal. Chem. Lett.* 2017, 7(1), 76-85. DOI: 10.1080/22297928.2017.1279567.
 34. Shukla, A.; Chhalotiya, U.; Shah, D.; Tandel, J.; Kachhiya, H.; Parmar, M. Development and validation of stability indicating HPTLC method for simultaneous estimation of dapagliflozin and linagliptin. *Discover Chemistry.* 2024, 1, article no. 4. DOI: 10.1007/s44371-024-00002-0.
 35. Bhatkar, K.A.; Waghulkar, V.M.; Jadhao, M.P.; Game, M.D.; Jawarkar, S.G. Analytical method development and validation for simultaneous estimation of antidiabetic drugs in bulk and marketed formulation. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences.* 2024, 2(5), 524-531. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11183408.
 36. Shukla, A.; Chhalotiya, U.; Shah, D.; Tandel, J.; Kachhiya, H.; Parmar, M. Simultaneous estimation of dapagliflozin and linagliptin using reverse phase-HPLC with photo diode array (PDA). *Journal of Chemical Metrology.* 2024, 18(1), 19-29. DOI: 10.25135/jcm.104.2401.3020
 37. Sowmya, P.S.; Krishna, V.S. Analytical method development and validation of dapagliflozin and linagliptin tablets by RP-HPLC. *YMER.* 2023, 22(4), 923-941.
 38. Waghmare, A.D.; Kolhe, S.D.; Sakshi, B.; Aishwarya, H. Development & simultaneous estimation method of linagliptin and dapagliflozin by UV spectrophotometry & HPLC in its API form. *Journal of Novel Research and Innovative Development.* 2025, 3(4), a207-a224.
 39. Agrawal, N.; Pathak, S. Eco-friendly UV spectrophotometric method for simultaneous estimation of evogliptin and metformin hydrochloride in bulk and combined tablet dosage form. *Braz. J. Anal. Chem.* 2022, 9(37), 140-150. DOI: 10.30744/brjac.2179-3425.AR-47-2022.
 40. Kalyankar, T.; Wadher, S.J.; Gholve, R.; Anitha, K. UV Spectrophotometric estimation of diclofenac potassium and omeprazole magnesium in bulk and combined tablet dosage form. *Int. J. Medi Pharm Res.* 2016, 2(1), 42-53.
 41. Yadav, M.; Chauhan, R.; Singh, R.; Tiwari, N. UV-Spectrophotometric approach for concurrent assessment of sitagliptin and dapagliflozin. *Afr. J. Bio. Sci.* 2024, 6(9), 1024-1032.
 42. Patel, R.D.; Maheshwari, D.G. Dual wavelength spectrophotometric method for simultaneous estimation of torsemide and amiloride hydrochloride in their combined dosage form. *Der Pharmacia Lettre.* 2014, 6(2), 43-49.

43. Attia, K.A.M.;Elabasawy, N. M.;Abolmagd, E. Simultaneous equation and area under the curve spectrophotometric methods for estimation of cefaclor in presence of its acid induced degradation product; A comparative study. *Future Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*.2017,3,163-167.DOI: 10.1016/j.fjps.2017.06.001.
44. Ghorpade, S.A.;Sali,M.S.;Kategaonkar, A.H.; Patel, D.M.;Choudhari, V.P.;Kuchekar, B.S.Simultaneous determination of emtricitabine and tenofovirby area under curve and dual wavelength spectrophotometric method.*J.Chil. Chem. Soc.*2010,55(1),115-117. DOI: 10.4067/S0717-97072010000100027.
45. Deka, M.K.;Ansary, A.; Das, T.K.; Das, A.K.;Sahariah, B.J.;Majumder, M.Development of three UV-spectroscopic methods for simultaneous estimation of raloxifene and aspirin in pharmaceutical dosage form: Whiteness and greenness assessment with application of ComplexGAPI, AGREE, and RGB. *Green Analytical Chemistry*.2024,8,100088. DOI: 10.1016/j.greeac.2023.100088.
46. Sen, D.B.;Jatu, S.;Maheshwari, R.A.;Zanwar, A.S.;Velmurugan, R.; Sen, A.K.New Eco-friendly UV-spectroscopic methods for simultaneous assessment of dapagliflozin, saxagliptin and metformin in ternary mixture. *Ind. J. Pharm. Edu.Res.*2023,57(2),559-569. DOI: 10.5530/ijper.57.2.69.

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